

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University,
Czech Republic

**Title: SOP for GC Thermo Trace 1310 - ISQ 7000:
Advanced Troubleshooting**

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Authors: Hana Seličová, Kateřina Coufalíková

Summary

This section describes the Troubleshooting of the most common problems occurring on GC ISQ 7000. Their solving needs at least basic skills in instrument maintenance. If necessary, check the official documentation for the instrument for more illustration.

IMPORTANT

Always make a note about all of the changes and replacements into the Logbook on the desktop of the ISQ computer.

HOW TO FIND IF THE ION SOURCE NEEDS TO BE REPLACED FOR CLEAN ONE?

1. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → View Tune Report (if was Tuned before) → Page 2 (Figure 1)

NOTE: For tuning, check the "[SOP for GC ISQ 7000 Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system](#)". For daily checking of the systém check the „[SOP for GC Thermo Trace 1310 - ISQ 7000: Daily maintenance and Checking of the system](#)“)

2. Check: Repeller Voltage, Lens 1 Voltage, Lens 2 Voltage, Lens 3 Voltage

NOTE:

- Repeller Voltage: default = 3 → OK; = 5 → still OK, but change would be needed soon; = 8 → change the source
- Lens – write down the values after first tune after changing the source and observe the changes and the trend – the value can't be said absolutely, depends on the comparison and settings.

- Other parameters on the Page 2 are for the Quadrupole – do not really need to check those.

ISQ Tune Results

Lab: Recetox
Tune Completed - Fri Jun 14 10:52:44 2024
Tune File: AutoTune_EI_2024-06-14-10-52-44.isqtune
Tune Type: EI Tune_HANKA
Starting Tune File: (Last Saved Tune)

Instrument Name: ISQ
Instrument ID: 2104078
User: ISQ7000

Tune Settings

Device	Mass	Value
Repeller Voltage	219	3
Lens 1 Voltage	68	-50
Lens 2 Voltage	131	-3.75
Lens 3 Voltage	219	-21.5
Ion Guide RF Amplitude	40	12.3
Ion Guide RF Amplitude	68	15.72
Ion Guide RF Amplitude	219	66.63
Ion Guide Voltage	40	-2.4
Ion Guide Voltage	68	-2.4
Ion Guide Voltage	219	-8.8
Q1 Entrance Lens	40	-2.4
Q1 Entrance Lens	68	-2.4
Q1 Entrance Lens	219	-8.8
Q1 RF Amplitude	9	5.46
Q1 RF Amplitude	1100	735.46
Q1 Voltage	68	-3.1
Q1 Voltage	219	-3.6
Q1 Resolution	68	0.0
Q1 Resolution	219	-0.01

Figure 1 - AutoTune Report - Checking the Ion Source

COLUMN BLEEDING CHECK IN AIR & WATER / TUNE

1. Set the temperature of the Oven for standby temperature for the specific column.

NOTE: This temperature differs between column types.

- DB-Sil5 columns = up to 80 °C
- more sensitive columns like WAX = approximately 40 °C.

2. ISQ 7000 Dashboard → Air & Water / Tune → Full Scan spectra → Remember or write down the Peak Intensity.

NOTE: Air & Water / Tune operation is described in detail in [“SOP for GC ISQ 7000 Single Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer - Turning on, calibration, tuning, and shutting down the system”](#).

3. Repeat steps 1 and 2 in the range of temperatures: initial temperature of the oven program, temperature of the last analyte, the final temperature of the oven program.
4. If the Peak Intensity is increasing → **column is BLEEDING at that temperature.**
5. If the Peak Intensity is still the same or similar → **column is still OK at that temperature.**

NOTE: Bleeding is important to check mainly in the temperature range of the desired analytes. Above that some amount of bleeding is expected since it is destroying of the column with higher temperatures. This is also why the tuning is done on low temperatures of the Oven.

TROUBLESHOOTING: If the column is bleeding in the temperature range of your analytes → exchange the column.

SHREDDED LINER IN PTV INLET – how to solve and clean the inlet

In case liner shred inside of the GC inlet during the installation or removing / changing the liner.

1. Put GC in Standby condition.

NOTE: In GC Thermo Trace 1310, there is no option how to manually put the instrument into the Standby condition. It will automatically go into this state once the machine is not measuring anything. You can see this stated on the Display of the GC in the lower part.

2. Cool down the oven and injector to room temperature via the GC Screen:
Maintenance button → select the inlet where the liner is → Click on “No”, it will turn into “Yes” → Begin Cooldown, the oven will be automatically cooled down too.

3. Wait till the GC and PTV are both cooled down to at least 40°C.
4. Prepare aluminium foil to which you will lay on the components.
5. Unscrew the septum cap (Figure 3), put it on the aluminium foil.
6. Use tweezers to remove the septum and bin it
7. Remove liner cap with slotted stubby driver and put it on the aluminium foil
8. Try to carefully remove the liner using the elongated dark pink tool provided in the kit for the manipulation with the liner.
9. If it does not go out and feels stuck, find the Cleaning kit from Restek (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - Inlet cleaning kit from RESTEK, illustratory, contents may be different

10. Turn off the gas flow – possible on the screen of GC via Instrument control → Front inlet (PTV) → Gas flow → Off **or** in Chromeleon → tab Front inlet → On → Off.
11. Remove the bottom parts of the injector (Figure 3):
 - Remove column from the inlet by unscrewing and removing the split nut holding ferrule and pulling down for the column
 - Put beaker below the inlet in the GC Oven as shards from broken liner may fall out of the inlet to the GC Oven

- Unscrew the Terminal Fitting for Capillary Column and remove also the Silver Seal (Figure 3).

12. Take the Cleaning kit from RESTEK, take curette (the metal handle with needle from both sides) and try to push the shredded liner out from the bottom of the PTV injector from the GC Oven.
13. If it does not work, the breaking of the liner is necessary.

IMPORTANT NOTE: Keep the beaker below the inlet to catch shards and solvents. Take protective glasses as shards from the liner may also go up to your face and endanger you.

- Take the wire cleaning metal brush with inner diameter corresponding to the liner from the Cleaning Kit from Restek.
 - Put the wire cleaning metal brush into the liner and by slow rotatory movement shred the liner to shards.
 - Using a pipe cleaner (furry wire), remove the possible glass fragments from the vaporization chamber.
14. Clean the PTV with solvent – just pour little amount of the solvent (acetone, methanol) in and with aid of the pipe cleaner clean the tube properly from residual shards.
 15. Reinstall the terminal fitting with the silver seal, tighten properly.

NOTE: This spot is very often the place where most of the leak on PTV happens. Really tight properly.

NOTE: Check if the silver seal is not oddly flat or curved. If yes, exchange for new piece. It is a consumable.

16. Install a new liner.

- Take the new PTV liner from the box
- Ensure you have it the correct way around – the wool should be in the upper half of the liner.
- Take Liner Seal and put it carefully on the liner without touching the liner endings.

- Put the liner into the inlet carefully, you should hear a glass “click” once the liner reaches the end of the inlet.

NOTE: If you don’t hear anything, there is chance you have the Liner Seal too low and the liner hasn’t reached the end of inlet. Readjust and try again.

- Put back the Liner cap and screw it tight with the slotted stubby driver.
- Put on the septum ideally without touching the injection part.
- Screw back the Septum cap and close the lid.

17. Reinstall the analytical column to the PTV inlet.

- Put the red septum on the column, then the PTV ferrule and on it the Split nut (Figure 3).
- Cut the column clean and check with the magnifying glass.
- Check if the distance of the bottom part side of the PTV ferrule is exactly 30 mm far from the end of the column.
- Put the column gently into the Terminal fitting.
- Screw the Split nut to the Terminal fitting using ¼” wrench.

NOTE: Screwing of the split nut requires to have a feeling for it – this part is very easy to overtighten. Go slightly “below” the complete tightening.

Figure 3 - PTV injector components

BURNED FILAMENT – HOW TO RECOGNIZE IT?

1. Needs to be checked on both filaments – switch them in Dashboard ISQ → Instrument control → Filament Selection → 1 → 2 (Figure 4)

Figure 4 – Filament changing from 1 to 2 or opposite way

2. It can be checked through the Dashboard ISQ → Analyzer, Filament tab (Figure 5). There is Filament condition, that should be on OK and also the Filament Current, that should be around 1,3 A. Emission current is set by user, in our case default to 50 μ A.

NOTE: While not measuring or the filament is off, the current will be obviously 0. If you want to check condition of your filament even if not measuring, turn on the Air & Water/Tune → Start Scan → Full and the Filament current should immediately jump on.

Status	Analyzer	Power	Maintenance
		Actual	Set Point
Temperatures			
✓	MS transfer line temp:	250 °C	250 °C
✓	Ion source temp:	250 °C	250 °C
✓	Ion optics temp:	248 °C	248 °C
✓	System over temp:	OK	
Repeller			
	Repeller voltage:	3.0 V	3.0 V
Filament			
✓	Electron lens voltage:	4.9 V	5.0 V
✓	Electron energy:	71.3 V	70.0 V
✓	Emission current:	50.0 μ A	50.0 μ A
✓	Filament current:	1.30 A	
✓	Filament condition:	OK	

Figure 5 - Filament condition checking

3. If the filament is not performing well (not saying OK, filament current lower or machine just doesn't measure at all = no sensitivity), **the filament is BURNED** and the exchange is needed. For more information about the exchange of filament, check out the manual for the MS.
4. If the filament has all the parameters OK, problem will be elsewhere – may be old multiplier.
- Check the Multiplier voltage and Detector gain each Checking of the machine
 - Above 2100 V the multiplier needs to be exchanged.

NOTE: Those parameters won't be find in the ISQ 7000 Dashboard directly, for checking of those the EI Check needs to be done: ISQ 7000 Dashboard → AutoTune → EI Check (or Custom version of this) → Start. Once this is done, this information will be on the first page of tune file.

NOTE: Exchange of the multiplier could not be made by user, call technicians for that.

NOTE: After exchanging the multiplier only check and tuning needs to be done. The custom tuning could be also used. You need to observe mainly the ability to reach all needed masses and the already mentioned parameters – Multiplier voltage and Detector gain. For the new multiplier they should be:

- Multiplier voltage – should start at 1200 V or slightly below (the higher the number, the higher is the multiplier trying to ramp up the voltage to enhance sensitivity; this parameter highly relies on background and cleanness of the ion source)
- Detector gain – $1,5 \times 10^5$